

SUPPLEMENTARY APPENDIX:

REHARMONIZATION GRAMMAR RULES IN JAZZ IMPROVISATION

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S1. Corpus of analyzed improvisations

Song	Artist	Key
You and the night and the music	Bill Evans	Cm
Summertime	Bill Evans	Am
A Foggy Day	Red Garland	Cmaj
The days of wine and roses	McCoy Tyner	Fmaj
Not You Again	Brad Mehldau	Ebmaj
Stella By Starlight	Keith Jarrett	Bbmaj
Bye Bye Blackbird	Red Garland	Fmaj
Dolphin Dance	Bill Evans	Ebmaj
Parisian Thoroughfare	Bud Powell	Fmaj
Everything happens to me	Bill Evans	Bbmaj
Pannonica	Chick Corea	Cmaj
New York Attitude	Kenny Barron	Dm
Days of Wine and Roses	Wynton Kelly	Fmaj
Peri's Scope	Bill Evans	Cmaj
The Girl From Ipanema	Oscar Peterson	Dbmaj
When lights are Low	Red Garland	Ebmaj
Blue In Green	Bill Evans	Gm
There is no greater love	McCoy Tyner	Ebmaj
Driftin	Herbie Hancock	Ebmaj
All the things you are	Hank Jones	Abmaj
Four	Herbie Hancock	Ebmaj
If I Should Lose You	Keith Jarrett	Bbmaj
All of You	Herbie Hancock	Ebmaj
Autumn Leaves	Wynton Kelly	Gm
On Green Dolphin Street	Bill Evans	Ebmaj
Toys	Herbie Hancock	Dm

Song	Artist	Key
I Thought About You	Herbie Hancock	Fmaj
Introspection	Thelonious Monk	D
Take the A' Train	Oscar Peterson	C
Softly, as in a morning sunrise	Oscar Peterson	Cm

S2. Annotation protocol

- **Unit of logging:** Observations are indexed by bar/beat/sub-beat codes (e.g., 10.4c–11.1a), optionally marked for R.H./L.H.
- **Primary evidence:** Existing transcription sources plus manual verification against the recording for the analyzed passage.
- **Uncertainty handling:** Ambiguous harmony / possible transcription error is explicitly flagged and may exclude a case from reharmonization extraction.
- **Annotator:** All annotations were produced by the first author, with verification against the recordings; ambiguous cases were explicitly flagged.
- **Scope:** The protocol targets chord-symbol-level transformations (not voice-leading realization), consistent with the rule representation used in the paper.

S3. External validation improvisations

Song	Artist	Key
All the Things You Are	Art Tatum	Abmaj
All the Things You Are	Tommy Flanagan	Abmaj
Autumn Leaves	Marcus Roberts	Gm
Autumn Leaves	McCoy Tyner	Gm
Beautiful Love	Bill Evans	Dm
But Beautiful	Bill Evans	Dbmaj
Cherokee	Art Tatum	Bbmaj
Donna Lee	Kenny Kirkland	Abmaj
How Deep Is the Ocean	Tommy Flanagan	Fmaj
How High the Moon	Tommy Flanagan	Gmaj
I Loves You Porgy	Bill Evans	Fmaj
If I Were a Bell	Oscar Peterson	Abmaj
I'll Remember April	Keith Jarrett	Gmaj

Song	Artist	Key
Just in Time	McCoy Tyner	Bbmaj
My Funny Valentine	Bill Evans	Cm
Night and Day	Bill Evans	Ebmaj
On a Clear Day	Wynton Kelly	Fmaj
On Green Dolphin Street	Bill Evans	Ebmaj
Perdido	Oscar Peterson	Bbmaj
Satin Doll	Bill Evans	Bbmaj
Satin Doll	McCoy Tyner	Cmaj
Someday My Prince Will Come	Bill Evans	Bbmaj
Stella by Starlight	Keith Jarrett	Bbmaj
Tenderly	Art Tatum	Dmaj
Tenderly	Oscar Peterson	Bbmaj
The Way You Look Tonight	Keith Jarrett	Fmaj
These Foolish Things	Art Tatum	Ebmaj
Wee Dot	Tommy Flanagan	Cm
What Is This Thing Called Love	Red Garland	Cmaj
What Is This Thing Called Love	Red Garland	Fmaj

per_start_pool_size = 1,200; global_pool_size = 6,000; calibrate_target = True

• **Returned outputs:** $K_{out} = 9$

S4. Reharmonizer default settings and ranking objective

All prototype outputs were generated with a bounded derivation search under fixed defaults. Candidates are expanded only when rule-context predicates hold, and generation is bounded by (i) a best-first expansion cap and queue cap, and (ii) a length policy tied to the user target length. Outputs are filtered by hard constraints (locks/anchors, length policy, chord-legibility checks) and ranked by a weighted score combining compactness, redundancy control (discouraging repeated use of the same method family), and harmonic plausibility, before deduplication/novelty gating and returning the top candidates with derivation traces.

- **Defaults used (Normal preset):**
- **Search bounds:** max_expansions = 12,000 per start; max_queue = 90,000
- **Length policy:** enforce_length_policy = True; mode = “adjust”; allow_shortening = False
- **Compute preset (Normal):** n_starts = 16; max_seconds = 2.5; per_start_results = 30;